

LESSON IN A MODERN SCHOOL: PROBLEMS AND WAYS OF THEIR SOLUTION

Uktamjonova Rayxona Farkxodjon kizi
student, Fergana State University, Uzbekiastan

Abstract: This article examines the current state of lesson practice in schools with a focus on identifying the main problems and finding ways to solve them. The authors analyse the current challenges facing teachers in lesson delivery, including a lack of attention to individual student needs, lack of interactivity and innovation, and problems of motivation and engagement. The article suggests practical approaches and strategies for overcoming these obstacles in order to improve the effectiveness of the learning process and the quality of education.

Keywords: classroom practice, school, problems, solutions, education, individual needs, interactivity, innovation, motivation, engagement, effectiveness.

Now, in improving the quality of education, not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the whole world, great attention is paid to educating children and giving knowledge to young people. Of course, the starting point of the foundation of this knowledge is the school.

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the decree "On additional measures to improve the public education management system".

It is noted in the document that the introduction of effective mechanisms for the management of the public education system is the most important condition for raising the spiritual, moral and intellectual development of the young generation to a new level in terms of quality, as well as in the educational process will help to apply innovative forms and methods of lim.

A modern school should prepare a person who thinks and feels, who not only has knowledge, but also knows how to apply this knowledge in life, who knows how to communicate, who has internal culture. The goal is not for the student to know as much as possible, but for him to be able to act and solve problems in any situation. There are also problems in which students move to a higher grade and teachers also change. After that, the child is not interested in the lesson and stops reading. The reason for this is that the child does not pay attention to the lesson, the teacher cannot interest and attract the child to the lesson.

Another reason for this is that the student who has passed to the upper class chooses his future profession and does not pay attention to the lesson. Focuses on subjects in which he is a specialist.

My proposal regarding this problem is that I think that private schools that prepare students for their specialty should be opened from the 5th grade, and admission should be based on an exam. Only then mature specialists who know their field well will develop. As one example, I can cite Presidential schools.

One of the ways to keep students interested in the lesson is to use ICT effectively. Through this method, the lesson becomes interesting, useful and attracts the attention of students;

ICT didactic material is diverse in content and form. The most used are: photos (reproductions) of the electronic encyclopedia "Cirilla and Methodius", videos, clips of songs, melodies, presentations on a certain topic, various tests, developmental assignments. The use of computer tests and game tests in the lesson allows the teacher to have an objective idea of the level of mastery of the studied material in a short time and to correct it in time. Lessons using ICT can not only relieve emotional stress and revitalize the learning process, but also increase learning motivation.

Mastering computer technologies for teachers is becoming an urgent need. These technologies enrich the arsenal of teaching methods, provide the teacher with rich visual material, make the lessons more colorful and interesting, and naturally contribute to better learning of students.

Multimedia tools such as slides, presentations or video presentations have been around for a long time and are not new. A computer is now capable of manipulating sound and video to achieve special effects, synthesizing and playing back sound and video, including animation, and combining them all into a single multimedia presentation.

Therefore, young people's interest in computer technologies starts at a young age. A characteristic feature of the educational process using information technologies is that the center of activity is the student, who builds the learning process based on his personal abilities and interests. The teacher often acts as an assistant, consultant, encourages original discoveries, encourages activity, initiative, independence. The effectiveness of using the available opportunities of using information technologies is clearly visible.

How to organize the use of modern information technologies in Russian language classes in primary grades? The optimal option appears when there are 1-2 computers in a primary school classroom. In this case, when the teacher is making a plan for any lesson, he can provide a stage where several students perform tasks on the computer by taking turns or working in groups. When using a multimedia projector, it will be possible to perform frontal work using new information technologies in primary school.

The teacher plays an active role in conducting the presentation lesson. The basis of the lesson is the presentation of new material illustrated with drawings, simple and

animated diagrams, animated and video films. The search for materials for the lesson is done in advance. All selected materials are combined into a general presentation, often using Power Point. During the lesson, such a presentation can be shown using a multimedia projector or on separate computers.

Russian language lessons use the capabilities of special programs that allow you to test your knowledge of vocabulary words and take tests on the topics being studied. Explain the lesson not only from the Grammar side, but through life examples; For example, if natural phenomena, household items, events in daily life are explained through examples, the student will understand quickly, easily, without getting bored, and it will be appropriate for the purpose.

Through various methods related to the topic:

The "Brainstorming" method is more helpful in this.

Apart from these, special attention should be paid to "Lyric withdrawal". Because if it is used in the lesson, even the bored students will "come to life". That is, it will be possible for students to answer the questions they are interested in by giving their opinions, or to tell about their favorite poems.

I think that if the teacher uses the methods listed above effectively, the lesson will be conducted in accordance with the purpose.

It is necessary to bring up educated, ambitious, mature young people in our country, to realize that the role of teachers is very important in imparting knowledge to them. The rapid development of our country, facing the world, is definitely in the hands of the young generation, and every Uzbek child should understand that it is appropriate to feel and understand.

References:

1. Amdilyan A.K. Modern information technologies. - 1990.
2. Gilmanov S. Creative individuality of a teacher // Narodnoe Obrazovanie Obrazovanie. - 1999. - № 1/2. - C. 191-203.
3. Kuzmina N.V. Formation of pedagogical abilities. - Л., 1961.